

**PROCEEDINGS OF THE MAIDEN
INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE**

OF

**SCHOOL OF AGRICULTURE, FOOD AND
NATURAL RESOURCES (SAFNR)**

**OLUSEGUN AGAGU UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY (OAUSTECH), OKITIPUPA,
ONDO STATE, NIGERIA**

THEME:-

**SUSTAINABLE CLIMATE-SMART
AGRICULTURE IN THE WAKE OF FOOD
INSECURITY AND MIGRATION**

DATE: 13TH – 16TH NOVEMBER, 2023

**Eds: Akinyemiju, O. A., Faleyimu, O. I., Amakoroma,
E. R., Ogunjobi, J. A., Adeoye, A. A., Olusola, S. E.,
Ogunsusi, K., Fatoba, T.A., Olojugba, M.R., Ogidi,
C.O., Oyebode L. A., Owombo, P.T., Oladitan, T. O.,
Aminu, O.O., Francis S. D. and Aladeboyeje, A. I.**

*A Publication of the School of Agriculture, Food and Natural Resources
(OAUSTECH)*

ISBN: 978-978-784-440-3

Olunusi *et al.*, 2023

ASSESSMENT OF CONSUMERS' PREFERENCE FOR BUSHMEAT IN IBADAN METROPOLIS, OYO STATE, NIGERIA

Olunusi, B.O.^{*1}; Olunusi, P.A.²; Olawumi, A.T.³

¹Department of Wildlife and Ecotourism, University of Ibadan, P.M.B. 200284, Oyo State, Nigeria

²Department of Food and Nutrition, Tai Solarin University of Education, P.M.B 2118, Ijebu-Ode, Ogun State, Nigeria

³Department of Agricultural Sciences, Tai Solarin University of Education, P.M.B 2118, Ijebu-Ode, Ogun State, Nigeria

*Corresponding e-mail: brightolunusi@gmail.com Phone no: +234 810 7820 880

ABSTRACT

Bushmeat is a valuable forest product, providing income and protein for urban and rural dwellers. This study focuses on consumers' preferences for bushmeat in Egbeda, Ibadan, Oyo State. One hundred and eight copies of questionnaire were distributed to adults (18 years and above) who frequently consumed bushmeat. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. Results showed that most respondents (83.7%) were aged 20-50 years, with over half (56.5%) having tertiary education. The majority (70%) preferred bushmeat due to its nutritional value (77.8%), medicinal value (29.6%), and socio-cultural beliefs (48.1%). Grasscutter was the predominant choice of wild animal consumption at 66.7%, whereas both snakes and monitor lizards each accounted for 11.1% of primary consumption preferences. For a secondary choice, antelopes were most favored, making up 33.3% of selections. Bushmeat was sourced from restaurants/bars (46.3%), marketers (33.3%), hunters (25.8%), and self-hunting (18.5%). The favoured preparations were smoked at 49.1%, peppered or stewed at 43.5%, and freshly boiled at 7.4%. The study concludes that preference for bushmeat is influenced by nutritional value > socio-cultural beliefs > medicinal value. It recommends government policies to prevent over-exploitation and emphasizes strict hygiene and proper cooking to avoid zoonotic diseases.

Keywords: Consumers preference, Nutritional value, Sociocultural belief, Wild meat

1. INTRODUCTION

Bushmeat, which includes various wild animal species consumed by humans range from mammals, the most common, to reptiles, birds, and amphibians (Nasi and Fa, 2015). This meat can be prepared fresh or smoked, used in soups and stews, or roasted or fried. For many, particularly rural dwellers, the bushmeat trade serves as a crucial source of income (Loibooki, Hofer, Campbell and East, 2002).

Bushmeat provides not only income (Olunusi, Lameed, Olunusi and Akiwumi, 2022) but also food security and animal protein for rural and urban consumers, especially in areas with scarce alternative protein sources (Nasi and Fa, 2015). It is also considered richer in energy, protein, and micronutrients than plant-based food (Alves *et al.*, 2016). In one study, decreased access to wild meat was linked to increased anemia rates among children in rural Northern Madagascar (Golden *et al.*, 2011).

Many consumers in Africa prefer bushmeat, viewing it as safer and better tasting than commercially produced meat, which may contain preservatives (Van Vliet and Mbazza, 2011). Additionally, bushmeat has zootherapeutic uses. Different parts of wild animals are combined with other ingredients to treat various ailments, from anaemia and hypertension to chest and joint pains (Agbogidi, 2010; Hanse and Teron, 2012; Martinez, 2013; Chowdhury *et al.*, 2014).

However, threats such as human population growth, land encroachment, overexploitation, and profit-driven trade risk the

extinction of wildlife in Africa (Wittemyer *et al.*, 2014; Akinsorotan *et al.*, 2020). Thus, sustainable hunting and trading practices are crucial for food security and healthy living.

The objective of this research is to delve into consumers' bushmeat preferences in the Oluyole and Egbeda LGAs, focusing on the prominent Odo-Ona and Asejire markets. These markets, vital in the bushmeat trade, provide insights into consumers' main motivations, encompassing nutrition, medicine, culture, and taste.

2. MATERIALS & METHODS

Study area: Egbeda LGA in Oyo State is located at longitude 30 58' E and latitude 7° 22' N, housing the Asejire market within its 11 wards, while Oluyole LGA, one of Oyo's oldest local governments, is positioned at latitude 7°13'59.99" N and longitude 3°52'0.01" E, and is home to the Odo Ona kekere bushmeat market in Ibadan.

Data Collection: Preliminary surveys were conducted on selected weekdays and weekends at both markets. Sellers were interviewed to ascertain the number of consumers they serve, and direct observation methods were used to count and validate the frequency of bushmeat consumers. Personal observations during on-site visits further provided insights into hygiene practices within these bushmeat markets.

Data Analysis: Collected data was subsequently analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. This analysis aimed to discern and interpret the respondents' characteristics and preferences in relation to bushmeat consumption.

Estimation Procedure: Based on the preliminary survey, we determined weekly consumer counts by selecting the highest daily count for each type, e.g., weekdays or weekends, to represent potential peak consumption. This maximum value approach was then aggregated for a weekly total, which was multiplied by four to estimate monthly bushmeat consumers for each market.

Sampling: From the estimated monthly population of bushmeat consumers (140 in OdoOna kekere and 220 in Asejire Market), 30% (n=108) was selected via purposive and convenience sampling. The inclusion criteria were adults aged 18 years and above who had consumed bushmeat and were willing to participate in the survey.

Assumptions:

1. Consumer frequency and market dynamics remain consistent throughout the study period.
2. The survey days represent a typical week's consumer behavior, and each consumer's visit is unique weekly.
3. The study recognizes potential biases from the sampling method and focuses exclusively on adult consumers.
4. All purchases are assumed for personal use, with consumers typically frequenting only one market monthly.
5. A 'consumer' is considered someone who completes a purchase.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

This research focused on bushmeat consumers in Egbeda and Oluyole.LGAs. The demographics in figure 1 indicated that most consumers were between 20-50 years old and highly educated, with the highest proportion (35.2%) belonging to the 31-40 age group. This finding aligns with a study by Chausson *et al.*, (2019), which reported that a significant percentage of bushmeat consumers were within the active age range.

Figure 1: Frequency Distribution of Age of bushmeat consumers

Percentage distribution of Bushmeat Consumers' Education

Figure 2: Percentage of Consumers' Education

In figure 2, more than half of the consumers (56.5%) had tertiary education, while 28.7% had secondary education and 14.8% had primary school education. This finding is consistent with the research conducted by Chausson *et al.* (2019) on urban bushmeat consumption, which also reported a high level of education among consumers. The occupation of the respondents varied across different spheres of life, including self-employment, private work, civil service, trading, and student roles.

PREFERENCE FOR BUSHMEAT COMPARED TO OTHER TYPES OF MEAT

Figure 3: Preference of bushmeat compared to other meat Bushmeat Consumption

All respondents consumed bushmeat regularly, with 70% preferring it over other meat types (Figure 3), aligning with findings by Van Vliet *et al.* (2017). The majority (77.8%) cited its nutritional value (Figure 4), recognizing bushmeat as a rich protein and micronutrient source (Van Vliet *et al.*, 2011; Niyi, 2014). Certain bushmeat varieties, like Grass cutter and blue duiker, were also noted for their health benefits (Adeyeye *et al.*, 2012; Mananga *et al.*, 2015).

About 29.6% mentioned bushmeat's medicinal value, reflecting the common practice of zoo therapy, including in Nigeria (Alves and Rosa, 2013; Chowdhury *et al.*, 2014; Van Vliet *et al.*, 2017). Also, 48.1% cited socio-cultural beliefs as a reason for their preference, emphasizing bushmeat's role in indigenous communities and its association with prestige (Sirén, 2012; Chausson *et al.*, 2019).

DETERMINANTS OF BUSHMEAT CONSUMPTION

Figure 4: Determinants of

As first choices, Grasscutter (66.7%) was the most popular type of bushmeat, with snake and monitor lizard (11.1% each) also being favorites (Figure 5). As for second choices, 33.3% of the respondents preferred antelope, 7.4% preferred bush-pig, grass cutter, and squirrel, and 3.7% chose bat, bush rabbit, civet cat, and crocodile. It is worth noting that 29.6% of the bushmeat consumers did not have a second-choice preference. These findings coincide with Nasi and Fa's (2015) research, indicating a preference for mammalian bushmeat.

Figure 5: Frequency distribution of bushmeat in order of consumers' preferences

Table 1: Frequency Distribution on the consumer mode of purchase, preservation, preference, knowledge on domestication and extinction of wildlife

Questions	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Where do you often get the bushmeat from:			
Marketers	Yes	36	33.3
	No	72	66.7
Hunters	Yes	28	25.9
	No	80	74.1
Restaurant and Bars	Yes	50	46.3
	No	58	53.7
Killing by Self	Yes	20	18.5
	No	88	81.5
What form of Bushmeat do you prefer?			
	Fresh	8	7.4
	Smoked	53	49.1
	Peppered / stewed	47	43.5
What Influence your choice?			
	Taste	104	96.3
	Price	4	3.7
Do you know that over-exploitation of bushmeat can cause an imbalance in the ecosystem of wildlife?			
	Yes	80	74.1
	No	28	25.9
Can you consider the domestication of wildlife to prevent the extinction of some of these animals?			
	Yes	96	88.9
	No	12	11.1

Restaurants and bars were the main sources of bushmeat, accounting for 46.3%, while only 18.5% of individuals sourced it through self-hunting. The most favored bushmeat preparations were smoked and peppered or stewed, predominantly chosen for their taste. These findings align with prior studies (Cowlshaw, 2005; Chausson *et al.*, 2019). Around 74.1% of respondents were aware of the potential ecosystem imbalance caused by over-exploitation (Wittemyer *et al.*, 2014), and 88.9% were open to wildlife domestication as a solution.

On-site observations suggested a need for improved hygiene practices, as outlined by Van Vliet *et al.* (2017), particularly in bushmeat preparation and consumption. This is especially crucial for smoked, peppered, and stewed meats to prevent the transmission of zoonotic diseases, such meats should be thoroughly cooked, processed, and stored under appropriate conditions.

The study has limitations, including its geographically specific scope, potential response bias, and limited perspective from other stakeholders in the bushmeat trade. Therefore, caution should be taken when generalizing these findings. Despite these, the research provides a foundation for further studies and policy development concerning sustainable bushmeat trade.

4. CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

This study establishes that factors like nutritional value, medicinal benefits, taste, and sociocultural beliefs drive bushmeat preference among consumers. As the demand continues, the trade will persist. To ensure sustainable bushmeat trade and consumption, government policies should address wildlife over-exploitation.

Strict hygiene in handling and preparation of bushmeat is also vital to minimize health risks and zoonotic disease transmission. Proper policies and hygiene standards can help balance bushmeat demand, wildlife conservation, and public health, contributing to sustainable bushmeat trade.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We thank Mr. Adeboye Tope for his assistance with the data collection process.

6. REFERENCES

- Adeyeye, E., Olaofe, O., and Ogunjana, K. (2012). Lipid profiles of the skin, muscle, and liver of greater cane rat (*Thryonomys swingerianus*): dietary implications. *Elixir Food Science*, 53;11749-1175.
- Agbogidi, O.M (2010). Ethno-botanical survey of the non-timber forest products in Sapele Local Government Area of Delta state, Nigeria. *African Journal of Plant Science*, 4(6), 183-189.
- Alves, R.R.N, Feijó, A, Barboza, R.R.D, Souto, W.M.S, Fernandes-Ferreira, H, Cordeiro-Estrela, P, and Langguth, A (2016). Game mammals of the Caatinga biome. *Ethnobiology and Conservation*, 5;1-51.
- Alves, R.R.N, and Rosa, I.L (2013). Introduction: Toward a Plural Approach to the Study of Medicinal Animals. In: Alves RRN Rosa IL (eds) *Animals in Traditional Folk Medicine: implications for conservation*. Springer-Verlag BerlinHeidelberg, pp. 1-9.
- Akinsorotan, O., Olaniyi, O., Oguntuase, B. and Raheem, T (2020). Dynamics and Socioeconomic Drivers of Illegal Hunting of Wildlife Animals for Consumption in Oba Hills Forest Reserve in Southwest Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Science Environmental Management*, 24(2), 287-298.
- Chausson, A., Rowcliffe, M., Escouflaire, L., Wieland, M., and Wright, J. (2019). Understanding the Sociocultural Drivers of Urban Bushmeat Consumption for Behavior Change Interventions in Pointe Noire, Republic of Congo. *Human Ecology*, 47:1791.
- Chowdhury, R., Warnakula, S., Kunutsor, S., Crowe, F., Ward, H.A., Johnson, L., Franco, O., Butterworth, A.S., Forouhi, N.G., Thompson, S.G., Khaw, K.T., Mozaffarian, D., Danesh, J., and Angelantonio, E. (2014). Association of dietary, circulating, and supplemental fatty acids with coronary risk systematic review and meta-analysis. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 160(6), 398-406.

- Cowlshaw, G., Mendelson, S., and Rowcliffe, M.R. (2005). Structure and Operation of a Bushmeat Commodity Chain in Southwestern Ghana. *Conservation Biology*, 19(1), 139–149.
- Golden, C.D., Fernald, L.C.H., Brashares, J.S., Rodolph Rasolofoniaina, B.J., and Kremen, C. (2011). 'Benefits of wildlife consumption to child nutrition in a biodiversity hotspot'. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, USA*, 108: 19653–19656.
- Hanse, R., and Teron, R. (2012). Ethno zoological practices among the Karbi tribes in Karbi Anglong district of Assam (India). *The Eco Scan*, 1: 117-120.
- Loibooki, M., Hofe, r H., Campbell, K., and East, M.(2002). Bushmeat hunting by communities adjacent to the Serengeti National Park, Tanzania: the importance of livestock ownership and alternative sources of protein and income. *Environmental Conservation*, 29(3). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0376892902000279>
- Mananga, V., Elenga, M., Massamba, D., Makosso- Vheiyé, G., Maloumbi, M., and Kinkela, T. (2015). Étude comparée de la biodisponibilité et de la valeur nutritionnelle des triacylglycérols des lipides de l'athérure africain (*Atherurus africanus*) et du céphalophe bleu (*Cephalophus monticola*). *Bulletin de la Société Royale des Sciences de Liège*, 84: 14-25.
- Martinez, G.J. (2013). Use of fauna in the traditional medicine of native Toba (qom) from the Argentine Gran Chaco region: an ethno zoological and conservationist approach. *Ethnobiology and Conservation*, 2:1-43.
- Nasi, R., and Fa, J. *The Role of Bushmeat in Food Security and Nutrition*. XIV World Forestry Congress, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/281407361>
- Niyi, O. (2014). Nutritional and functional properties of African wild antelope (*Antilocapra americana*) meat. *American Chemical Science Journal*, 4(4): 546-553.
- Olunusi, B. O., Lameed, G.A., Olunusi, P.A., Olawumi, A.T. (2022). Socioeconomic determinants of hunters' participation in bush meat trade in Ibadan Oyo State Nigeria. *Journal of Biotechnology and Biodiversity*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.20873/jbb.uft.cemaf.v10n1.olunusi>
- Sirén, A. (2012). Festival hunting by the kichwa people in the Ecuadorian amazon. *Journal of Ethnobiology*, 32(1): 30-50.
- Van Vliet, N., and Mbazza, P. (2011). Recognizing the multiple reasons for bushmeat consumption in urban areas: a necessary step toward the sustainable use of wildlife for food in Central Africa. *Human Dimension of Wildlife*, 16(1): 45-54.

- Van Vliet, N., Moreno, J., Gómez, J., Zhou, W., Fa, J., Golden, C., Alves, R., Nasi, R. (2017). Bushmeat and human health: Assessing the Evidence in tropical and sub-tropical forests. *Ethnobiology and Conservation*, 6 (3): 1-45.
- Wittemyer, G., Northrup, J.M., Blanc, J., Douglashamilton, I., Omondi, P., Burnham, K.P. (2014). 'Illegal Killing for Ivory Drives Global Decline in African Elephants'. *Proceedings of The National Academy of Sciences USA*, 111: 13117-13121.